

WFNN 2017 Congress Report

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Australia wins bid for 2021 WFNN congress

Australian nurses celebrated as they were announced winners of the next congress destination at the recent 12th Quadrennial Congress in Opatija, Croatia. The congress destination will be Darwin Australia, on the Northern coast of

Australia.

Darwin is the largest city in the Northern Territory with exceptional opportunities to experience Aboriginal culture and the natural beauty of the Australian coast. We hope to see you there in 2021!

After four years of planning, the WFNN Congress in Opatija, Croatia has come to a successful completion.

As Scientific Chair of the Congress, the quality and range of abstracts was comprehensive and we tried to showcase a varied international cross-section, as this congress saw speakers from all corners of the globe. The program itself comprised 4 plenary sessions, 4 morning satellite sessions, 86 concurrent sessions and 72 posters.

There were over 450 delegates, including 46 Australians. The Australian contingent included 14 speakers and 6 presenting posters, a great representation from ANNA.

The Scientific Program commenced with an outstanding Pre-Congress workshop conducted by Linda Littlejohns entitled "What is wrong with my patient? Tying assessment of stroke, trauma and degenerative disease to 3D anatomy" using the computerised Anatomage table. Linda's association with WFNN has been lengthy and is always a great learning experience.

WFNN and the Neurocritical Care Society came together to offer the ENLS (Emergency Neuro Life Support) course for delegates prior to the start of the Congress. This was a successful offering and will be considered prior to each Congress.

The Social program was built into the Scientific Program, with half day outings to - Rovinj & Agrolaguna Vineyards; Brijuni National Park; Island of Krk & Vrbnik Wine Region; and Pula & the Olive Oil Museum.

Some countries have more resources than others and whilst the languages may differ, the process behind neuroscience nursing does not. Similar issues are faced the world over. Conferences like this one offers a great opportunity for networking and making new friends. However, a Congress such as this cannot run without the dedicated support of a great team of people, most of whom are volunteers. The respect and admiration for these people cannot be measured and professional and personal associations have been enhanced by this experience. Get involved and you'll reap the rewards. The networks you make will last for years and the friends forever.

Lastly, but most significantly, the WFNN Board of Directors, voted almost unanimously that the next Congress will be held in **Darwin, Australia 2021**. So let's make that Congress "the best ever"!

